

**THE KEEPERS OF MEMORY:
PRIESTS IN UKRAINIAN
IMMIGRATION TO BRAZIL**

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ABSTRACT. This work intends to investigate the collective memory over the Ukrainian community in Brazil. The general goal is analysing what makes the Ukrainian culture in Brazil be so religious. For this purpose, a brief approach will be done about the relation between collective memory and culture. After it, the

Ukrainian traditions are presented. Then the Ukrainian immigration to Brazil becomes the target, being highlighted the adaptation and the challenges of this ethnic group in the new land, mainly the dispute of influence that occurred involving priests and the intelligentsia. It raised the following problem: *Why does the collective memory of the Ukrainian community in Brazil have a high degree of religiosity?* The research group have adopted the exploratory method with bibliographic review and direct observation techniques. The provisional answer for the question (hypothesis) is because who exercised the leadership to keep alive the collective memory of Ukrainians in Brazil were the priests. There was a validation of it.

KEYWORDS: Collective memory, culture, priests, traditions, Ukrainians.

INTRODUCTION

This work intends to investigate the collective memory over the Ukrainian community in Brazil. Bearing in mind the concern of delimitation, two cuts were done. One of temporal nature and other of spatial one. The former was adopting 1891 as the starting point, what is justified to the fact of this year being considered the landmark of

the Ukrainian immigration to Brazil (Antonelli et al 2021, p. 19). The later was studying the theme within Paran, once is where the majority of the Ukrainian community lives in Brazil (Carvalho et al 2011, p. 139).

Before the problem *Why does the collective memory of the Ukrainian Community in Brazil have a high degree of religiosity?*, there was raised a hypothesis. Basically it is because who exercised the leadership to keep alive the collective memory of Ukrainians in Brazil were the priests and other missionaries as well.

The choice for this theme has a double relevance. The social relevance in reason to deal with an ethnic group that helped the Southern Brazil to get development in socioeconomic and cultural dimensions. The scientific relevance is based on the Public Call 03/23 of the Applied Social Sciences Mastership Programme at the State University of Ponta Grossa (UEPG). It created the project "Traditional Knowledges and Brazil-Ukraine Cooperation for the Center-South Paran Development" whose one of the scopes is favouring the knowledge production about the expressions of social questions in local, regional and national spheres. The refered project represents the participation of State University of Ponta Grossa with the Araucria Foundation through a wider public policy: The Paran Program for Hosting the Ukrainian Scientists (Carvalho et al, 2023).

As there are many other topics that still were not studied by the research group about collective memory, we understood the appropriate method to use on this investigation was the exploratory. It allowed us to know better the own chosen issue and gave us flexibility to write the text. In regard the techniques, since the beginning of the project a plenty of sources was consulted among books, articles and papers, a significant part of them provided by Mr. Vitrio Sorotiuk, the president of Ukrainian-Brazilian Central Representation (UBCR). Moreover, we also traveled to localities where the cultural heritage is practiced, what justifies the direct observation use here.

COLLECTIVE MEMORY AND CULTURE

Related to abstract concepts, collective memory and culture have a deep connection. Although the last has been studied for a long time in the academia, the former is more current. According to Gurios (2012, p. 11), the expression "collective

memory” was created by Maurice Halbwachs during the 20’s. This French sociologist underlined that the memory should be understood as a collective and social phenomenon, being collectively built and submitted to constant transformations (Ramos et al, 2020, p. 175).

This idea of constant transformation does not sound weird for those who study the culture. It is well-known in the cultural anthropology, especially by Melville J. Herskovits and his theory of culture that one of the principles which guides the culture is exactly its dynamic adjective (HERSKOVITS, 1963, p. 32). About the memory itself, maybe other fields that deal with its nature like philosophy, psychology, psychoanalysis and neurosciences (GUÉRIOS, 2012, p. 15) could show an easier explanation to detect this constant transformation. Mainly in the individual sphere as Belim (2023, p. 83) does when describes her sense while was having a trip among orchards with her «Бабуся». What at the moment was ordinary for her, later became a memory full of romantic fantasies reminding Taras Shevchenko’s poems.

Focusing on the collective memory, the fields of anthropology, history and sociology are more adequate do investigate it. Despite of it, Halbwachs tried to solve a confusion many people do, that is not distinguishing collective memory from the historic science memory. If it does not have a function with the identity question, the opposite is seen on the collective memory that is a kind of guarantee for a group existence (ASSMAN, 2011, p. 144), what also shapes the “ethos” of this group in the way theirmembers see themselves (MONTERO, 2022, p. 225–226).

UKRAINIAN TRADITIONS IN BRAZIL

Ukrainians brought many things when arrived in Brazil. In the words of Herskovits (1963, p. 33)when defined what means culture, those things things would be a «body of tradition (s)». It is possible to split this body of traditions into two categories. Basically Traditional Knowledges (TKs) and Traditional Cultural Expressions (TCEs), if we take into account the proposal from the Convention on Diversity of Cultural Expressions in regard intangible cultural heritage (UNESCO, 2005). All of these things only could be maintained through the generations feeding the collective memory. Although TKsand TCEs are passed orally showing the hearing

sense exercise, the collective memory embodies other sensorial perceptions (ASSMAN, 2011, p. 25).

«Вареники», «борщ», «голубці», «коровай», «крашанка» and «паска» are some examples of Ukrainian food that appear in Southern Brazil cuisine. How would be their destiny if the older family members had not taught their descendents their recipes? According to Morais (2011, p. 243 apud Ramoset al, 2020, p. 155), typical food is not any food because represents lived experiences and establishes a bridge with those who live in the present. It is a case of memory behind the taste perception awaking feelings. In this way, it is useful to mention again Belim's book. The writer underlines her perception of smell of traditional flowers in Ukrainian countryside. The same happens when she visited the Rushnyk Museum in Poltava while was touching an embroidery of «white the white» style.

Antonelli et al (2021, p. 61) sustain the Church had played a role beyond its social scope of managing the religion. Currently is not more the only place where the members of the Ukrainian community meet each other, but surely continues to have a central position like Guérios (2012, p. 156) observed in respect to the 1st wave of Ukrainians to Brazil. It was confirmed during the visits that our research group have done across Paraná Center-South: The church as a promoter of Ukrainian TKs and TCEs. For instance, in Mallet the existence of classic TCEs of festive events as «Гаїлка» and «Івана Купала». are under the Churches Saint Michael Archangel and Holy Heart of Jesus, respectively. Musical liturgy with «Самоїлка» and «Глас» continue to be part of the ritual in communities like Saint Nicholas inside Saltinho 1 in Ivaí. In addition to, traditional embroidery (rushnyk) participates not only in the Greek-Catholic church decoration as well as the Orthodox one, like was seen in the two Ukrainians churches of Ponta Grossa.

THE RELIGIOSITY AS A SOURCE OF SURVIVAL IN THE NEW LAND

Ukrainians who came to Brazil in 1890's were most part from Galicia (Галичина), a territory where in that time was under Austro-Hungarian jurisdiction (Antonelli et al, 2021, p. 112). Although it concerned a multi-ethnic state (Guérios,

2012, p. 35), it was far away to be considered a positive thing in that circumstance because of the dominance of some nations over the others, like Polish power disturbing any possibility of a Rutenian emancipation in Prague during the 1st Pan-Slavic Congress in 1848. However, Ukrainians would not face this type of problem in Brazil. What made bad to them was a gap of support by the Brazilian State of helping them to be adapted into the colonies. Facing many challenges of survival, letters were sent to Ukraine asking for priests coming to the region for the aim of preserving their beliefs and values (Antonelli et al, 2021, p. 25–26). They ended up to be those who taught literacy for the immigrants what Guérios (2012, p. 183) named in the quality of “education promoter” and they also played a responsibility that would suit for diplomats (Burko, 1963, p. 53).

As pointed Guérios (2011, p. 80–81), the clergy had many advantages over the intelligentsia in leading the peasants. Basically they were in permanent contact with them, and comparing the arrival of the first priest with the intelligentsia members in Brazil, there is a difference of 11 years. While the first Ukrainian priest to arrive in Brazil was Nicolau Michalevitch on June of 1896 (Antonelli et al, 2021, p.24), the engaged immigrants to Society *Provista* in Galicia only come in 1907 (Guérios, 2011, p. 77). In some way the priests influence on the peasants was easier, once the superstitious aspect in almost all the Ukrainian cultural traditions.

CONCLUSION

As was briefly presented here and will be more worked through the whole article, the collective memory of Ukrainian immigration to Brazil carries strong similarities to their motherland. Since 988 A.C when Ukraine was Kyivan Rus' its body of traditions was affected with Voldymyr The Great's decision to christianize his empire (Burko, 1963, p. 24). Then through the centuries the pagan traditions were celebrated as christian ones.

Whereas the priests helped to build schools, talked to the Brazilian authorities looking for defend the immigrants and essentially fed Ukrainian TKs and TCEs, it seems the provisional answer above that who exercised the leadership can justify why a culture here has so many religious traits.

REFERENCES

Antonelli, D., Choma, A., & Seniuk, T. (2021). *Ucrânias do Brasil: 130 anos de cultura e tradição ucraniana*. Curitiba : Máquina de Escrever.

Assman, A. (2011). *Espaços da recordação: formas e transformações da memória cultural*. Traduzido por Paulo Soethe. Campinas : Ed. Da Unicamp.

Belim, V. (2023). *Minha Ucrânia: a jornada de uma mulher em busca da história de sua família e de seu país*. Traduzido por Alessandra Esteche. Rio de Janeiro : Record.

Burko, V. (1963). A Imigração Ucraniana no Brasil. *Tese (Doutorado em Jornalismo) – Universidade Internacional de Estudos Sociais “Pro Deo”*. Roma.

Carvalho, E. de., Saes, K. V. R., & Meza, M. L. F. G. de. (2023): When academic displacement and internationalization intersect, different approaches for inclusion in Higher Education. *Revista Interdisciplinar da Mobilidade Humana*, 31:68, pp. 133–148.

Guerios, P. R. (2012). *A imigração ucraniana ao Paraná: memória, identidade e religião*. Curitiba : Ed. UFPR.

Herskovits, M. J. (1963). *Antropologia cultural: man and his works*. 8ed. Traduzido por Carvalho e Bichels. São Paulo : Ed. Mestre JOU.

Montero, A. S. (2022). Los usos del *ethos*: abordajes discursivos, sociológicos y políticos. *Rétor*, Vol. 2, No. 2, pp. 223–242.

Ramos, O. F et al. (2020). *Prudentópolis: cultura, história e identidade*. 1ed. Guarapuava : Ed. Da Unicentro.

Szewciw, I. (1988). *O milênio do cristianismo na Ucrânia*. Traduzido pela Eparquia Ucraniana de São João Batista. Curitiba : Gráfica Vicentina Ltda.

UNESCO (2005). *Convention on the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions*. Available at: <https://www.unesco.org/en/legal-affairs/convention-protection-and-promotion-diversity-cultural-expressions>.